

Welcome to the Security on Mobile Devices survey

Thank you for participating in our survey. Your feedback is important.

The term "mobile device" indicates a portable computing device such as a smartphone or tablet computer.

The aim of this survey is to collect opinions on security methods from current users of mobile devices. The information will be used for an academic study to analyse scenarios that might occur in real life, and understand the best solution needed to protect sensitive personal data on mobile devices.

Try to be as honest as possible when answering the questions.

Demographics

1. Are you male or female?

- Male
 Female

2. What is your age?

- 18-20
 21-29
 30-39
 40-49
 50-59
 60 or older

3. What kind of operating system are you currently using on your mobile device(s)?

- Android
 iOS
 Windows
 Other (please specify)

4. What model of mobile device are you currently using? Please, feel free to indicate the model of each device you are using if it's more than one. (e.g. Samsung S6, iPhone 5S etc.)

Sensitive Data

'Sensitive personal data' is defined in Section 2 of the UK Data Protection Act as personal data consisting of information relating to the data subject with regard to racial or ethnic origin; political opinions; religious beliefs or other beliefs of a similar nature; trade union membership; physical or mental health or condition; sexual life; the commission or alleged commission by the data subject of any offence; or any proceedings for any offence committed or alleged to have been committed by the data subject, the disposal of such proceedings or the sentence of any court in such proceedings.

5. Do you consider that you currently store sensitive data on your mobile device?

- Yes
- No
- I'm not sure

6. Can you indicate on a scale from 1 (Not at all important) to 5 (Extremely important), how important the protection of each of the following elements on your mobile device is to you?

	Not at all important	Not important	Neither important or not	Important	Extremely important
Emails \ Messages (e.g. SMS) \ Notes content	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Specific apps, such as those with sensitive information or potential financial use	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Contacts	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Photographs	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Calendar	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Social Networks	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Memberships \ Travel cards	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Browsers	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Can you indicate if there is something that we haven't specified that you would like to protect on your mobile device?

Face Verification

Face Verification

Face verification is concerned with validating a claimed identity based on the image of a face, and either accepting or rejecting the identity claim (one-to-one matching).

7. Have you ever used a face verification system before?

- Yes
- No

Voice Verification

Voice Verification

Voice verification is concerned with validating a claimed identity through his or her "voice print", a numerical representation of the sound, pattern, and rhythm of an individual's voice.

8. Have you ever used a voice verification system before?

- Yes
- No

Fingerprint Verification

Fingerprint Verification

Fingerprint verification refers to the automated method of verifying a match between two human fingerprints. The analysis of fingerprints for matching purposes generally requires the comparison of several features of the print pattern.

9. Have you ever used a fingerprint verification system before?

Yes

No

Mobile device data protection

10. What kind of security do you currently have on your mobile device(s)?

- Password
- Alphanumerical password
- Alphanumerical password with special characters
- PIN (a numerical code, usually consisting of four digit code)
- Unlock Pattern (a draw created by connecting, at least, four dots in vertical, horizontal or diagonal directions in a scheme)
- Biometrics (defined as the automated recognition of individuals based on their biological and/or behavioural characteristics)
- I don't use any security methods
- Other (please specify)

11. What kind of security methods have you experienced on a mobile device?

- PIN
- Pattern
- Password
- Face verification
- Voice verification
- Fingerprint verification
- Other (please specify)

12. Can you indicate the level of trust you might have if using each of the following methods on your mobile device?

	I wouldn't trust this method at all	I wouldn't trust this method	Not sure	I would trust this method	I would trust this method for sure
Password	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
PIN	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Pattern	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Face verification	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Voice verification	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Fingerprint verification	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Mobile device data protection

13. Can you indicate how likely you would be to use the following security methods on your mobile device for each scenario?

	Password	PIN	Pattern	Face Verification	Voice Verification	Fingerprint Verification
Unlock the screen of your mobile device	<input type="text"/>					
Access to a particular app on your device (For instance for calling or messaging)	<input type="text"/>					
Make a purchase online with your mobile device (e.g. Amazon, eBay)	<input type="text"/>					
Make a bank transfer with your mobile device	<input type="text"/>					
Buy something online on your mobile device	<input type="text"/>					
Access to Google services such as Google now or Google maps	<input type="text"/>					
Access to your social networks	<input type="text"/>					

Iris Verification

Iris Verification

Iris verification is an automated method of biometric identification that uses images of one or both of the irises of an individual's eyes, whose complex random patterns are unique, stable, and can be seen from some distance.

14. Have you ever used a iris verification system before?

- Yes
- No

Gait Verification

Gait Verification

Gait verification is defined as the identification of a person through the pattern produced by walking: it has been shown that a subject's gait pattern is sufficiently unique for identification.

15. Have you ever used a gait verification system before?

- Yes
- No

Vein Verification

Vein Verification

Vein verification uses the vascular patterns of an individual's palm/finger/dorsal of the hand as personal identification data.

16. Have you ever used a vein verification system before?

- Yes
- No

Continuous Authentication

Continuous Authentication

Continuous authentication is the process of verifying the identity of a user repeatedly during the use of a mobile device. Generally, continuous authentication methods assume that the process of authentication is unobtrusive; this is necessary as it is impractical to require users to explicitly authenticate themselves at recurring intervals.

17. The list below gives some examples of information that can be used as means to authenticate the user in a non-intrusive way. With regards to obtrusiveness, how happy would you be to use each of the following pieces of information for continuous authentication on your mobile device?

	Very unhappy	Unhappy	Neither happy or unhappy	Happy	Very happy
Text on messages or emails	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
App usage	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
GPS positions	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Touch dynamics (the way you use the touchscreen of your device)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The way you hold your device	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Mobile Device Data Protection

The following questions relate to the use of innovative biometric methods to secure mobile devices. Some of them have already been implemented, others have been tested and are ready to be used. With the progression of technology, high-quality cameras can now be implemented on mobile devices and be used for iris and vein verification. As mobile devices have different sensors, different kinds of data can be collected from the internal gyroscope and the accelerometer and can be used to recognise someone by the way they walk or hold the device. Touchscreen, GPS, and the keypad can provide information on an individual and be used for continuous authentication.

18. Can you indicate the level of trust you might have if using each of the following methodology on your mobile device?

	I wouldn't trust this method at all	I wouldn't trust this method	I am not sure	I would trust this method	I would trust this method for sure
Iris verification	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Gait verification	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Vein verification	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Continuous authentication	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

19. Can you indicate how likely you will use the security methods on your mobile device for each scenarios?

	Iris Verification	Gait Verification	Vein Verification	Continuous Authentication
Unlock the screen of your mobile device	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>
Access to a particular app on your device (For instance for calling or messaging)	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>
Make a purchase online with your mobile device (e.g. Amazon, eBay)	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>
Make a bank transfer with your mobile device	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>
Buy something online on your mobile device	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>
Access to Google services such as Google now or Google maps	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>
Access to your social networks	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>